

A flow-box theorem in \mathbb{R}^2 through a homotopy of diffeomorphisms

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Abstract

We introduce a generalization of the rectification problem (which results into propositions are defined as "flow-box theorems") in the Euclidean plane, in which the application of a diffeomorphism that transforms a given vector field into a constant one is restricted to a maximal open set under a given property, which will be specified in the following explanation. Furthermore, this diffeomorphism is extended to a homotopy, such that, along a parameter in $[0, 1]$, the given vector field is continuously deformed into a constant one. In the construction of such a homotopy, we consider the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) rule applied to the Jacobian of a given differentiable map, together with a rearrangement of some of the elements of the matrices arising in this decomposition.

1 Introduction

The problem of rectifying vector fields frequently arises in Geometry and Mathematical Analysis; for a primary reference, see V. I. Arnold's *Ordinary Differential Equations* [1]. It concerns the idea that, given a differentiable vector field X in \mathbb{R}^n , it is possible to find a diffeomorphism $\Phi : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ whose pushforward applied to X yields a nonzero constant vector field.

Arnold himself [1] considers as a fundamental theorem (called "The basic theorem of the theory of ordinary differential equations", Chapter 2-7.1) one of the key local results: namely, if in \mathbb{R}^n the vector field X is locally non-vanishing at a point p , then X at p is diffeomorphic to the constant field $e_1 = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$. That is, if U is a neighborhood of p in \mathbb{R}^n , there exists a diffeomorphism f from U onto some $V \subset \mathbb{R}^n$.

There exists a series of theorems concerning this topic under different and restricted conditions (referred to as "flow-box theorems") [2, 3, 4], and in [5] there exists an explicit formula of the above-mentioned general result, which is "the basic theorem of the theory of ordinary differential equations", (reported in [1]). In the following, we present an approach to the problem in \mathbb{R}^n within a domain as large as possible (which we call *maximal*), also considering a family of diffeomorphisms forming a homotopy from the identity to a diffeomorphism whose pushforward rectifies the given vector field.

2 Selection of Differential Map

Consider a vector field $X : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ which is nowhere vanishing, and aim to construct a homotopy $\Phi' : [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ of diffeomorphisms that rectifies X to the constant vector field $e_1 = (1, 0)$, i.e. $D\Phi'_0 X = e_1$ and $\Phi'_1 = \text{Id}$.

Let A be the matrix-valued function associating to each point in \mathbb{R}^2 the matrix (X, X^\perp) , where X^\perp is the vector field orthogonal to X , obtained by rotating X by $\pi/2$ clockwise. That is, if $X = (a_1, a_2)$, then:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ -a_2 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let F and F^\perp be the families of integral curves of X and X^\perp , respectively. If Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 denote the corresponding flows, then:

$$F = \{\Psi_{1x} \mid x \in \mathbb{R}^2\}, \quad F^\perp = \{\Psi_{2x} \mid x \in \mathbb{R}^2\}.$$

Consider the curve γ in F passing through 0. Define a map Φ as follows: for each $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$, let p' be the endpoint (other than 0) of the arc of γ of length x starting at 0. Let $\delta(p')$ be the curve in F^\perp passing through p' , and let p be the endpoint (other than p') of the arc of $\delta(p')$ of length y starting at p' . Then:

$$\Phi(x, y) = \Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x), y).$$

3 Selection of the Domain

Let us consider a domain on which to operate with Φ following the previous discussion. To do this, consider the following family of open sets \mathcal{D} in \mathbb{R}^n , where \mathcal{A} denotes the collection of open subsets of \mathbb{R}^2 :

$$\mathcal{D} = \{A \in \mathcal{A} \mid \forall \gamma_1 \in F|_A, \forall \gamma_2 \in F|_A^\perp : |\gamma_1 \cap \gamma_2| = 1\}$$

Where $|\cdot|$ denotes the cardinality of a set (in the discrete sense) or, otherwise speaking, the number of its elements. This is the family of open sets in which the intersection of every pair consisting of an integral curve of X and one of X^\perp is reduced to a single point. So \mathcal{D} turns out to be partially ordered. Moreover, consider an increasing chain \mathcal{C} of open sets in \mathcal{D} :

$$C_0 \subset C_1 \subset C_2 \subset C_3 \subset \dots \subset C_{n-1} \subset C_n \subset \dots$$

and let A_0 be the union of all elements of \mathcal{C} . Suppose that there exist $\gamma' \in F|_{A_0}$ and $\gamma'' \in F|_{A_0}^\perp$ such that $|\gamma' \cap \gamma''| \neq 1$. For every $i \in \mathbb{N}$, let $\gamma'_i \in F|_{C_i}$ and $\gamma''_i \in F|_{C_i}^\perp$ be such that $\gamma'_i = \gamma'|_{C_i}$ and $\gamma''_i = \gamma''|_{C_i}$. If $|\gamma' \cap \gamma''| = 0$, then for every $i \in \mathbb{N}$ we obtain $|\gamma'_i \cap \gamma''_i| = 0$, but this is false since γ'_i and γ''_i are flow lines in C_i , an open set in \mathcal{D} . On the other hand, if $a_1, a_2 \in \gamma' \cap \gamma''$ with $a_1 \neq a_2$, then there exist $i_1, i_2 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $a_1 \in C_{i_1}$ and $a_2 \in C_{i_2}$. Without loss of generality, assume $i_1 \leq i_2$, so that $a_1, a_2 \in C_{i_2}$. Hence,

$$a_1, a_2 \in \gamma'_{i_2} \cap \gamma''_{i_2},$$

but since $C_{i_2} \in \mathcal{D}$ and $a_1 \neq a_2$, this leads to a contradiction (the case $i_2 \leq i_1$ is analogous).

From this it follows that every increasing chain in \mathcal{D} admits an upper bound; therefore, by Zorn's lemma, \mathcal{D} admits at least one maximal element. Let us select such a chain \mathcal{D}_0 with $0 \in C_0 \in \mathcal{D}_0$ and denote its maximal element with D_0 , which we will refer to in the following.

4 Construction of the Homotopy

Let us consider the map $\Phi|_{\Phi^{-1}(D_0)}$ (where it is understood that the codomain is restricted accordingly), with Φ defined in Section 2, and which for notational convenience I will henceforth denote simply by Φ . By definition, the function Φ is surjective onto the whole D_0 . Let us prove that Φ is injective; we know that each integral curve of $F|_D$ intersects each curve of $F|_D^\perp$ in exactly one point.

Thus, considering $(x, y), (x', y') \in \Phi^{-1}(D_0)$, we have that if $x \neq x'$, then $\Psi_1(0, x) \neq \Psi_1(0, x')$, since the integral curves are not cyclic (a consequence of a historical results reported by Bendixson [6] and of the fact that X is a planar vector field which is nowhere vanishing). Now, if the curves $\Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x), \cdot)$ and $\Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x'), \cdot)$ had the same image, they would intersect $\Psi_1(0, \cdot)$ at $\Psi_1(0, x)$ and $\Psi_1(0, x')$, since $\Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x), 0) = \Psi_1(0, x)$ and $\Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x'), 0) = \Psi_1(0, x')$, but such curves are orbits of X and X^\perp on D_0 , hence a contradiction follows and therefore $\Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x), y) \neq \Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x'), y')$.

Conversely, if $x = x'$, again by what is reported in [6] and since necessarily $y \neq y'$, one has $\Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x), y) \neq \Psi_2(\Psi_1(0, x'), y')$.

Let us consider A , defined previously, which is continuous on \mathbb{R}^2 , as well as A^n with $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Now we consider the Singular Value Decomposition in its orthogonal version, namely, for every square matrix N of order n , there exist two orthogonal matrices O, H of order n and a diagonal matrix L with positive entries, also of order n , such that:

$$N = OLH$$

Returning to A , it is associated with a pair of eigenvalues according to the SVD (which are not necessarily distinct); they vary continuously since the characteristic polynomial varies continuously with respect to \mathbb{R}^2 (a statement deduced from [7]).

Consider the function $\Omega : \mathbb{R}^{n+1} \rightarrow M_2(\mathbb{R})$, $\Omega(a, b_1, \dots, b_n) = aI + \sum_i b_i A^i$, which is a symmetric matrix with eigenvalues $a + \sum_i b_i \lambda_j^i$, with $j = 1, 2$.

Now consider the subdomain of D_0 , an open set, in which the eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 are distinct, with $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2$. Then, if r is a positive real number, $A^r = O \text{diag}(\lambda_1^r, \lambda_2^r) O^t$, and since $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \neq 0$, one has:

$$aI + bA = A^r$$

with:

$$a = \lambda_1^r - \frac{\lambda_1^r - \lambda_2^r}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \lambda_1,$$

$$b = \frac{\lambda_1^r - \lambda_2^r}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2},$$

since, carrying out the computations:

$$a + b\lambda_j = \lambda_j^r, \quad j = 1, 2.$$

On the other hand, in the subdomains of D_0 in which $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2$, one has:

$$a = (1 - r)\lambda_1^r,$$

$$b = r\lambda_1^{r-1}.$$

Considering the union of the two subdomains, one easily shows that a and b are continuous on the whole \mathbb{R}^2 , since:

$$\lim_{\lambda_2 \rightarrow \lambda_1} \left(\lambda_1^r - \frac{\lambda_1^r - \lambda_2^r}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \lambda_1 \right) = (1 - r)\lambda_1^r,$$

and:

$$\lim_{\lambda_2 \rightarrow \lambda_1} \frac{\lambda_1^r - \lambda_2^r}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} = r\lambda_1^{r-1}.$$

Now we have that A^r is pointwise orthogonal (not necessarily orthonormal, since:

$$A_1^r \cdot A_2^r = [a(1, 0) + bA_1] \cdot [a(0, 1) + bA_2] = ab(A_{12} + A_{21}) = 0.$$

Now consider, for each $r \in [0, 1]$, two vector fields X_r and X_r^\perp in D_0 , namely $X_r = A_1^r$ and $X_r^\perp = A_2^r$, and let Ψ_1^r and Ψ_2^r be the respective flows. Let also $Y(0, r) := (0, X_r)$ and $Y^\perp(0, r) = (0, X_r^\perp)$ be vector fields defined on \mathbb{R}^3 . Considering also the field $Y^0(0, r) = (1, 0, 0)$, we have that Y, Y^\perp, Y^0 form a set of orthogonal vectors; then, if $\Omega, \Omega^\perp, \Omega^0$ are the flows respectively of Y, Y^\perp , and Y^0 , analogously to Section 3, adapting the discussion to the case of \mathbb{R}^3 for Y, Y^\perp, Y^0 , define:

$$\Gamma(x, y, t) = \Omega^\perp(\Omega(\Omega^0(0, t), x), y).$$

Observing that:

$$\Omega^0(0, t) = (t, 0, 0),$$

and:

$$\Omega(p, x) = p_1 \times \Psi_1^{p_1}((p_2, p_3), x),$$

$$\Omega^\perp(p, y) = p_1 \times \Psi_2^{p_1}((p_2, p_3), y),$$

we obtain:

$$\Gamma(x, y, t) = \Omega^\perp(\Omega(\Omega^0(0, t), x), y) \tag{1}$$

$$= \Omega^\perp(\Omega((t, 0, 0), x), y) \tag{2}$$

$$= \Omega^\perp(t \times \Psi_1^t(0, x), y) \tag{3}$$

$$= t \times \Psi_2^t(\Psi_1^t(0, x), y) \tag{4}$$

$$= t \times \Phi_t(x, y). \tag{5}$$

Now, applying the same reasoning as in Section 3, there exists an open set E containing 0 which is maximal with respect to inclusion within the family based on the relation described in that section. Then:

$$\bigcup_{t \in [0, 1]} \{t\} \times D_0^t = E.$$

Moreover, in the same way for $t = 0$, for every t' , the restriction $\Gamma_{|\{t'\} \times \Phi_{t'}^{-1}(D_0^{t'})}$ is bijective (replicating the same argument of Section 3). In conclusion, Γ is bijective, that is:

$$\Gamma(\{t'\} \times \Phi_{t'}^{-1}(D_0^{t'})) = \{t'\} \times D_0^{t'}, \quad \forall t' \in [0, 1].$$

Finally, defining Γ' as:

$$\Gamma' : \bigcup_{t \in [0,1]} \{t\} \times \Phi_t^{-1}(D_0^t) \rightarrow E,$$

it is a homotopy of diffeomorphisms having Φ as initial map. Therefore, the statement is proved.

5 Conclusion

This treatment develops the rectification problem under very general assumptions. The aim is to extend the idea beyond the two-dimensional case and to explore analogies with Arnold's local theorem, especially in the presence of singularities. Further developments may include generalizations to differential equations and applications in dynamical systems, where rectification plays a significant role [1].

References

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